

Editorial

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Learning is a process that practically never stops and human life should be linked to this noble goal. There are two important days in a person's life, namely the day he was born and the day he becomes aware of why. Throughout this journey in which we manage to identify what is the source and what is the purpose of our life, we practically add with each new thing learned, with each new lived experience, we add something and we build a building.

When man comes into the world, he is at his maximum capacity to be able to gather and capitalize on everything he will learn. Practically from that moment man learns, from breathing, from smiling, from enjoying the little things, then he keeps accumulating and accumulating in a rhythm that is constantly increasing, but which also has moments of stopping, standing on certain platforms, also in order to accumulate, as in a climb on a mountain with certain challenges and which will lead you to an extremely beautiful goal and which will show why you have reached a certain place in life and what exactly you need to you do with everything you have accumulated until you become aware of your purpose. It can happen that the person does not realize these things and the importance of dedication to learn and to accumulate information only very late. It may happen that during the period when the person should assimilate a lot of information to consider that it is a shield for him.

Lifelong learning is a process that somehow takes place unconsciously, because it begins the moment the child opens his eyes to the world. The learning process begins first with imitation. The joy of discovery is always

extraordinary, but at every stage of life, man discovers differently and discovers in a certain way that changes him as a man, that changes him in the way he perceives things, but also in the way he relates. he to those new things discovered. Thus, the learning process must not stop and must diversify. In order for man to evolve, he needs to get out of his comfort zone and move towards challenges and not comfort. Comfort could be compared to those platforms on which you stop after making some accumulations, without continuing the accumulation path further, which will lead to capping and convenience without reaching the maximum potential.

If you have a good attitude and you want to not limit yourself, in terms of information, only to what educational institutions offer and discover you and if you want to know more about yourself, you will surely find resources within you to discover a multitude of new things.